

Molecular Dynamics Simulation of CO₂ Hydrate Growth and Intermolecular Weak Interaction Analysis

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Abstract: The growth of carbon dioxide (CO₂) hydrate in CO₂ aqueous solution (box A), and in CO₂ aqueous solution with structure I (sI) CO₂ hydrate cell as seed (box B) under the same conditions of 275 K and 10 MPa, were simulated respectively. The total simulation time is 5000 ns. The nucleation process is very slow, so it is difficult to observe CO₂ hydrate growth in box A without CO₂ hydrate seed, CO₂ just accumulates to form bubbles, while H₂O still remains liquid, the F4 order parameter remains about -0.1. By contrast, beautiful CO₂ hydrate in box B grows rapidly, CO₂ is trapped in the cages formed by H₂O molecules, F4 rises from 0.12 to 0.7 due to the formation of sI hydrate. The density of CO₂ hydrate in box B is as high as 1.25 g/cm³, higher than that of seawater, which is beneficial to its permanent sealing on the seabed. In box B, in accordance with the independent gradient model based on Hirshfeld partition (IGMH) analysis, a H₂O molecule forms four hydrogen bonds with surrounding H₂O molecules, CO₂ only has van der Waals interaction with surrounding water cages. In the actual large-scale CO₂ storage process, especially for the rapid storage of CO₂ in the form of hydrate, it is strongly recommended to pre-add CO₂ hydrate crystals into the solution to achieve the purpose of rapid growth of CO₂ hydrate.

Keywords: Molecular Dynamics; CO₂ Hydrate; Order Parameter; IGMH

29 In the past century, the average temperature of the earth has risen by 0.5~1 °C,
30 and the International Commission on Climate Change has announced that if the
31 current trends in fossil fuel use and deforestation are not reversed, the average
32 temperature of the earth would rise by about 6 °C in the 21st century[1-3]. In order to
33 protect the earth, the major powers in the world have taken various measures, such as
34 afforestation and developing clean energy, to cope with global warming.

35 Carbon dioxide (CO₂), as a kind of greenhouse gas, is the main factor leading to
36 global warming. Some researchers believe that the ability of afforestation to alleviate
37 global warming is limited[4], and sequestration of CO₂ is an effective method to
38 reduce CO₂ emissions. In July 2021, China Petroleum & Chemical Corporation
39 announced that the first megaton-level carbon capture and storage project in Qilu
40 Petrochemical Company and Shengli Oilfield would be build, which would be the
41 largest industrial chain demonstration base in China after being put into operation[5].
42 In August 2021, China National Offshore Oil Corporation announced that China's
43 first offshore CO₂ storage demonstration project has been officially launched, and
44 more than 1.46 million tons of CO₂ would be permanently stored in submarine
45 reservoirs in the Pearl River Mouth Basin of the South China Sea[6]. This is an
46 important step in the green and low-carbon transformation of offshore oil and gas
47 development in China, and explores a new way for China to achieve the goal of
48 "carbon peak and carbon neutralization".

49 It is an effective method to convert gaseous CO₂ into solid CO₂ hydrate for
50 storage, thus reducing carbon emissions. CO₂ hydrate is crystalline ice-like compound,
51 in which, CO₂ is trapped in polyhedral cells cages within H₂O molecules. In previous
52 reports, structure I (sI) hydrate is the most common in nature. The lattice parameter of
53 cubic sI hydrate cell is 1.205 nm, which consists of two small (5¹²) and six large (6²5¹²)
54 cages[7], the schematic diagram is shown in Figure 1. The small cages (pentagonal
55 dodecahedral) and large cages (tetrakaidekahedral) are composed of 12 pentagonal
56 H₂O rings and 12 pentagonal plus 2 hexagonal faces, respectively. The molecule
57 diameter of CO₂ is 0.512 nm, and it usually forms sI hydrate with H₂O, in which, CO₂
58 molecules can occupy large and small cages at the same time[8]. Many experimental

59 studies have examined the formation of CO₂ hydrate, and measured the effects of
60 pressure, temperature and additives on hydrate[9, 10]. At the microscopic level, many
61 scholars have use molecular dynamics method to simulate the formation or
62 decompose of natural gas hydrates, and explain its mechanism in detail[11]. Jana and
63 coworkers[12] performed molecular dynamics simulations of the formation and
64 growth of CO₂ hydrate in pure H₂O under 260 K and 50 MPa, by varying the CO₂
65 concentrations extensively. In pure water, the ratio of CO₂ to H₂O at 1:7 is found to be
66 an optimum concentration for rapid, complete, and well-ordered growth of CO₂
67 hydrate, with a total simulation time of 200 ns. It was this paper that inspired our
68 current research, we went a step further to investigate CO₂ hydrate in more details.
69 Jiang et al[13] performed systematic microsecond simulations to investigate the
70 nucleation of CO₂ hydrate. They claimed that the nucleation is closely related to the
71 hydration shells of CO₂ in H₂O, and only above a critical concentration will
72 nucleation occurs.

73 Although the researches in general literature are meaningful, the simulation time
74 is relatively short, only nanoseconds or close to microseconds, or the box does not
75 reach a complete stable state[11-14]. With the increase in computing power,
76 researchers found that longer simulation time is more in line with the actual
77 situation[15-17]. It can be seen from the references that the crystallization process of
78 H₂O can be divided into two stages: nucleation and growth, the nucleation process is
79 slow and the growth process is fast[13, 15, 18]. In order to make the crystal grow
80 rapidly and obtain the target morphology crystal, the simplest way is to add a small
81 amount of the target crystal as “seed” into the solution.

82 In this work, two simulation boxes were established, box A: CO₂ aqueous
83 solution; box B: CO₂ aqueous solution in which sI CO₂ hydrate is pre-added as a seed.

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Figure 1 Schematic diagram of small (5¹², a) and large (6²5¹², b) water cages in sI hydrate

86 **1 Simulation Software and Parameter Settings**

87 Gromacs[19] version 2019.6 was used for all atoms molecular dynamics (MD)
88 simulation, and sI CO₂ hydrate unit cell reported in reference [20] was used as seed,
89 which contains 46 H₂O molecules and 8 CO₂ molecules. Use Multiwfn[21] to adjust
90 the atom order and bond relationship of the CO₂ hydrate unit cell, and then expand the
91 ordered unit cell into a 2×2×2 periodic super cell[22], the obtained CO₂ hydrate super
92 cell contains 368 H₂O molecules and 64 CO₂ molecules (CO2ICE.pdb in supporting
93 information). Optimized potentials liquid simulation (OPLS-AA) force field[23] was
94 used for simulation. Three-point SPC H₂O model and EPM2 CO₂ model[24, 25] were
95 used for building simulation box. Box A: use packmol[26] to create a CO₂ aqueous
96 solution box directly, as shown in Figure 1A (input_box_A.inp in supporting
97 information), contains 1104 H₂O molecules and 192 CO₂ molecules. Box B: use
98 packmol to build the box as shown in Figure 1B (input_box_B.inp in supporting
99 information). The initial boxes sizes are both 2.5×2.5×7.5 nm, and the schematic
100 diagrams are shown in Figure 2.

101

102 Figure 2 Snapshot of box A and B, Y and Z axis of the boxes are shown in the figures, X axis is facing
103 the inside of the snapshot

104 Energy minimization: The steepest descent algorithm is used to minimize the
105 system energy, and periodic boundary conditions are applied in all three dimensions
106 (em.mdp in supporting information), and then the three-point H₂O model is
107 transformed into the four-point H₂O model, and TIP4P/Ice H₂O model[27] was used
108 instead. Although some H₂O models such as TIP4P[28] and TIP4P-EW[12], have
109 been used to simulate the formation or decomposition of hydrate in some literature, in
110 recent years, OPC H₂O model is considered as the best H₂O model[29]. In fact,
111 TIP4P/Ice is undoubtedly the most ideal model for the simulation of icing process[27,
112 30].

113 NPT (constant numbers of components, pressure, and temperature)
114 pre-equilibrium equilibration: The MD pre-equilibrium simulations is carried out by
115 using leapfrog algorithm, the pressure algorithm is Berendsen with pressure of 10
116 MPa, and the pressure control method is isotropic with a coupling constant time of 0.5
117 ps. The temperature algorithm was V-rescale with temperature of 275 K and a
118 coupling constant time of 0.2 ps [13]. The pressure and temperature are close to those
119 of 1000 meters of seabed environment. Long-range interaction is handled by the
120 particle mesh Ewald technique (PME), a cutoff of 1 nm is implemented for
121 Lennard-Jones, neighbor list generation method is Verlet, and only hydrogen bond is
122 constrained, random number seed is set to -1, initial velocity is set to 0, the
123 temperature corresponding to the initial velocity is set to 275K, long-range dispersion
124 correction is EnerPres, and total pre-equilibrium simulation time is 500 ps (npt.mdp in
125 supporting information).

126 MD production run: After the NPT pre-equilibrium simulation is completed, the
127 pressure algorithm is changed to Parrinello-Rahman, and other parameters remain
128 unchanged. Then, 5000 ns NPT generation phase simulation is performed (md.mdp in
129 supporting information), and visual molecular dynamics (VMD) version 1.9.3[31] is
130 used to display intuitive molecular dynamics and animate trajectories.

131 All simulations are performed on a NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080Ti GPU, all
132 input files are listed in the support information, so anyone can repeat our work as long
133 as they follow the commands.

134 2 Results and Discussion

135 2.1 Growth Process of CO₂ Hydrate

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Figure 3 Snapshot of the simulation process in box A

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As can be seen from Figure 3, as soon as the simulation start, CO₂ quickly gather to form bubbles, and there is no sign of icing. When the simulation time is extend to 141 to form bubbles, and there is no sign of icing. When the simulation time is extend to 142 5000 ns, no obvious change is observed, CO₂ still exists in the form of gaseous, and 143 water dose not crystallize. The result show that it is difficult to form hydrate under 144 these conditions. This is similar to Jiang's report[13] and different from Walsh's 145 report[15]. In Walsh's report, hydrate is visible when the simulation time reaches 146 about 1000 ns. This may be due to differences in temperature and pressure. The final 147 box size is 2.46790×2.46790×7.40368 nm, that is, 45.09234 nm³.

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Figure 4 Snapshot of CO₂ hydrate growth process in box B

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It can be seen from Figure 4, when the simulation time is 20 ns, it is obvious that 154 ice begins to grow and CO₂ aggregates into bubbles; as the simulation continues, CO₂ 155 enters cages formed by H₂O molecules. When the simulation reaches 500 ns, the

156 hydrate grows rapidly, and as the simulation time reaches 2000 ns, CO₂ hydrate is
157 completely formed; with the extension of the simulation time, the hydrate state
158 maintains unchanged. The final size of box B is 2.32330×2.32330×6.96989 nm, that
159 is, 37.62153 nm³, quit different from box A. In the case of the same number of
160 molecules in box A and B, the volume of box B is smaller than that of box A, so the
161 density would be different.

162

163 Figure 5 Density change of box A and box B in the simulation process

163

164 As can be seen from Figure 5, when the simulation starts, the density of box A
165 drops rapidly, and that of box B rises. The reason is that CO₂ in box A accumulate to
166 form bubbles, meanwhile, no hydrate is formed and there is no cages to trap CO₂. By
167 contrast, in box B, during the formation of CO₂ hydrate process, CO₂ enters the cages,
168 and its density rises, which can be regraded as an evidence of CO₂ hydrate formation.
169 As a metaphor, we fill a box with sand and continue to fill the sand gap with water.
170 The final density of box A is about 1.03 g/cm³, and that of box B is 1.25 g/cm³, which
171 is completely consistent with the report in reference[20]. When people seal CO₂ on
172 seabed in the form of CO₂ hydrate, because the density of CO₂ hydrate is higher than
173 that of seawater, the hydrate will spontaneously sink to the seabed and will not float
174 and decompose. This is really a match made in heaven.

175 From the above simulation, it can be concluded that in the presence of sI CO₂
176 hydrate as seed, the hydrate grows rapidly, which is beneficial for the rapid capture
177 and storage of CO₂. We also notice that in box B (video in supporting information),
178 the water begins to freeze as soon as the simulation start, but it is not clear from
179 snapshot, it will be further explained by the F4 order parameter and the number of

180 cages formed by H₂O molecules.

181 2.2 Number Density Distribution of Molecules in Z Direction

182 As can be seen from Figure 3 and Figure 4, the distribution of H₂O and CO₂
183 molecules in the two boxes is significantly different. In box A, CO₂ accumulates on
184 both sides to form bubbles; in box B, CO₂ enters the cages formed by H₂O molecules,
185 which appears to be distributed evenly.

186

187 Figure 6 Molecule number density distribution of H₂O and CO₂ in Z direction

188 With the center of the boxes as the origin, the molecule number density
189 distribution of H₂O and CO₂ in Z direction is shown in Figure 6. In box A, the number
190 density of H₂O molecules on both sides is extremely low, almost 0 nm⁻³, while the
191 number density of CO₂ molecules is large, about 13 nm⁻³; at the center of box A, the
192 number density of H₂O molecules is about 33 nm⁻³, and that of CO₂ is about 0 nm⁻³,
193 which is completely consistent with Figure 3. In box B, the average number density of
194 H₂O and CO₂ molecules in Z direction is about 30 nm⁻³ and 6 nm⁻³ respectively, H₂O
195 and CO₂ molecules are distributed evenly, which is completely consistent with Figure
196 4. Interestingly, molecule number density in box B are jagged, indicates that the
197 distribution is uniform and regular, rather than chaotic or flat style. In addition, it can
198 also be seen from Figure 6 that in the Z direction, the box length of box A is longer
199 than that of box B, indicating that the CO₂ hydrate in box B is “tighter” than in box A,
200 it is possible to cause a difference in density of the two boxes.

201 2.3 Radial Distribution Function Analysis (RDF)

202 The radial distribution function (RDF) can be used to describe the configuration

203 of hydrate structure. Considering a homogeneous distribution of atoms/molecules in a
 204 box, $g(r)$ represents the distance r of selecting an atom/molecule as a reference
 205 point, to the probability of finding another atom/molecule in a shell Δr , which can
 206 represent the order degree of the system.

$$207 \quad g_{\alpha\beta}(r) = \frac{V_s}{N_\alpha N_\beta} \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^{N_\alpha} \frac{n_{i\beta}(r)}{4\pi r^2 \Delta r} \right\rangle$$

208 Where $g_{\alpha\beta}(r)$ is the average probability that the particle β appears within the
 209 distance of r and $r + \Delta r$ away from the i th particle α . N_α and N_β are the
 210 numbers of particles α and β , respectively. V_s is the volume of the simulation
 211 box; r is the distance between two kinds of particles; $n_{i\beta}(r)$ is the number of
 212 particle β within the distance between r and $r + \Delta r$ away from the i th particle
 213 α .

214
 215
 216 Figure 7 Radial distribution function results (A: RDF between oxygen atoms in H₂O molecules; B:
 217 RDF between oxygen atoms in H₂O and carbon atoms in CO₂; C: RDF between carbon atoms in
 218 CO₂ molecules)

219 It can be seen from Figure 7A that the first peak of RDF between oxygen atoms
220 in H₂O is 0.25 nm, and the maximum value of $g(r)_{O-O}$ in liquid water is higher than the
221 peak of $g(r)_{O-O}$ in hydrate, indicating that liquid H₂O molecule move faster than H₂O
222 molecule in CO₂ hydrate, which is consistent with previous report[32]. In CO₂ hydrate,
223 $g(r)_{O-O}$ is abundant in detail, with two peaks at 0.43 nm and 0.62 nm, indicating the
224 second and third coordination layers. In contrast, liquid water has only the peak value
225 of the second coordination layer at 0.43 nm, but the third coordination layer is not
226 obvious, the waveform is flat and the value is close to 1, which shows that liquid
227 water is homogeneous and H₂O molecules are irregular. As shown in Figure 7B, the
228 curves distributions of $g(r)_{C-O}$ in the two boxes are significantly different. In box B,
229 $g(r)_{C-O}$ has a sharp peak at 0.4 nm, indicating that the average distance in the CO₂
230 hydrate between carbon in CO₂ and oxygen atom in H₂O is 0.4 nm, and the
231 distribution is regular. In box A, the unobtrusive broad peak around 0.4 nm is the
232 $g(r)_{C-O}$ distribution of H₂O and gas CO₂ at the H₂O-gas interface. Due to the gas-liquid
233 interface in box A, the distribution of CO₂ in H₂O is uneven, and there is no obvious
234 peak value in RDF curve. At the same time, we also noticed that in Figure 7C, the two
235 curves of $g(r)_{C-C}$ are of too much difference. In CO₂ hydrate (box B), an
236 unobtrusive peak appears at about 0.4 nm; while in box A, there is a remarkable
237 peak at about 0.4 nm. This is because in CO₂ hydrate, CO₂ molecules are distributed
238 in cages which formed by water evenly, and the distance between carbon atoms is
239 always about 0.65 nm. In gaseous CO₂ (box A), the average distance between CO₂
240 molecules is about 0.4 nm. This can be used as an evidence to distinguish liquid water
241 from gaseous CO₂ and from CO₂ hydrate.

242 **2.4 F4 Order Parameter**

243 When water freezes, H₂O molecules are arranged regularly, and the torsion angle
244 order H-O···O-H of two adjacent H₂O molecules can be described by F4 order
245 parameter, a function of the torsion angle between oxygen atoms within 0.35 nm and
246 the outermost hydrogen atoms in the H₂O-H₂O pair[33, 34]. As a classical order
247 parameter, F4 is widely used to describe the ordered structure of micro H₂O molecules,
248 and its calculation formula is as follow:

249
$$F_4 = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \cos 3\varphi_i$$

250 Where φ_i is the torsion angle between oxygen atom and hydrogen atom furthest
 251 from another oxygen atom in two adjacent H₂O molecules, and n_i is the number of
 252 oxygen atom in H₂O molecule within 0.35 nm. Theoretically, the average values of F4
 253 order parameter for sI hydrate, liquid water, and ice are 0.7 (for both sI and sII
 254 hydrate), -0.04 and -0.4, respectively, so F4 order parameter is an effective
 255 quantitative indicator of phase transition[15, 35].

256
 257 Figure 8 Variation of F4 order parameter with simulation time

258 In Figure 8, during the simulation progress, F4 order parameter in box A has no
 259 significant change and basically remains about -0.1, indicating that water remains
 260 liquid and there is no sign of freezing. In Walsh's report[15], methane aqueous
 261 solution can spontaneously form hydrate within 2000 ns at low temperature (260 K)
 262 and high pressure (45 MPa). However, in our work, due to the difference of
 263 temperature (275 K) and pressure (10 MPa), hydrate did not form even if simulation
 264 time reaches 5000 ns; perhaps differences in guest molecules (CH₄ and CO₂) also
 265 account for difference in icing rates. It is assumed that CO₂ hydrate might be formed
 266 by reducing temperature, increasing pressure or prolonging simulation time, but at a
 267 high cost. In box B, F4 order parameter rises rapidly, indicating the hydrate is
 268 undergoing a rapid growth. When the simulation proceeds to 1000 ns, F4 change rate

269 slows down, indicating that the hydrate has formed; when the simulation is carried out
270 to 2000 ns, F4 order parameter remains stable, indicating that the rapid hydrate
271 formation process has come to an end, even if the simulation time extended, the F4
272 order parameter remains unchanged. F4 is about 0.7 and it is perfect with Walsh's
273 report, it shows that CO₂ hydrate in line with the theory and expectation has formed.
274 This is consistent with the hydrate growth process shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

275 2.5 Number of Cages

276 We already know that CO₂ molecule is trapped in large (6^25^{12}) and small (5^{12})
277 cages formed by H₂O molecules in sI CO₂ hydrate. The cages number is also worth
278 investigating.

279

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Figure 9 Number of cages vs simulation time in box B

281 As shown in Figure 9, a critical observation is the absence of 6^45^{12} cages in the
282 hydrate growth process, which confirms pure sI CO₂ hydrate. The number of 6^25^{12}
283 cages are approximately three times that of 5^{12} cages. This also validates the
284 composition of the sI hydrate, which contains two small and six large cages in its unit
285 cell. In box A, no hydrate is formed, and the number of cages are always 0. In box B,
286 the average hydrogen bond lifetime is 41.9 ps; while in box A, the average hydrogen
287 bond lifetime is 19.53 ps. This shows that CO₂ hydrate is more stable than liquid H₂O
288 at the same temperature of 275 K and pressure of 10 MPa. For calculation details,
289 please see supporting information.

290 **2.6 Weak Interaction Analysis**

291 In box B, a water molecule and all surrounding 0.3 nm water molecules, a 5^{12}
 292 cage and a 6^25^{12} cage were selected for independent gradient model based on
 293 Hirshfeld partition (IGMH) [36] analysis, by using Multiwfn software[21]. ORCA
 294 version 5.0.1 software was used to obtain wave function information[37, 38], the
 295 single point energy calculation method were r^2 SCAN-3c[39], and input file was
 296 generate with the help of Multiwfn. In Figure 10, the blue bar indicates strong
 297 electrostatic or hydrogen bonding effect, the red bar indicates obvious steric hindrance
 298 effect, and the green bar indicates low average density value at corresponding position
 299 corresponding to weak effect, that is, dispersion effect. Only a few molecules that we
 300 are interested in are shown in Figure 10.

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302

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Figure 10 IGHM analysis of inter-molecule in box B

304 In Figure 10a, four blue isosurfaces formed by a H_2O molecule and surrounding
 305 H_2O molecules can be clearly seen. Among them, two blue isosurfaces near hydrogen
 306 atom in the middle H_2O molecules reflect the characteristics of two hydrogen atoms
 307 as hydrogen bond donors; two blue isosurfaces near the middle oxygen atom reflect
 308 the active trend and direction of the oxygen atom as hydrogen bond receptor. This is
 309 exactly the same as the analysis of sI ice reported in references[36]. While in Figure
 310 10b and 10c, CO_2 was trapped in a 5^{12} and 6^25^{12} cage, respectively. The discrete green
 311 isosurface indicates that the interaction between CO_2 molecule and surrounding

312 molecules is fairly weak (van der Waals interaction). As can be seen from Figure 10c,
313 in the large cage ($6^{25}12$), the van der Waals interaction between CO₂ and surrounding
314 H₂O molecules is so weak and negligible. The cage in Figure 10b corresponds to
315 Figure 1a, and Figure 10c corresponds to Figure 1b.

316 Although there is no hydrate formation in box A, the inter-molecule interactions
317 at the H₂O-gas interface are still worth studying.

318

319

Figure 11 IGHM analysis of inter-molecule weak interactions in box A

320 As can be seen from Figure 11, hydrogen bond and van der Waals interactions
321 also exist between molecules, but they are different from that shown in Figure 10. In
322 Figure 11a, there are three blue isosurfaces and one green isosurface, in which, the
323 green isosurface shows that this hydrogen bond is significantly weaker than the other
324 three hydrogen bonds. There is hardly interaction between CO₂ molecules in the gas
325 phase, and as a result, no isosurfaces can be seen in Figure 11b. At the interface
326 between H₂O and CO₂, there are only a few scattered green isosurfaces, which are
327 attributed to van der Waals interactions (Figure 11c).

328 **3 Conclusion**

329 The growth of CO₂ hydrate was simulated by molecular dynamics simulation
330 method. The cage number and F4 order parameter prove the formation of sI CO₂
331 hydrate, pre-adding hydrate seed to the target aqueous solution can greatly accelerate
332 the formation of hydrate, because the time-consuming nucleation process is directly
333 skipped, and the number of large cages ($6^{25}12$) is absolutely in dominant. In CO₂
334 hydrate, each H₂O molecule can form four hydrogen bonds with surrounding H₂O
335 molecules, and there is only van der Waals interaction between CO₂ and H₂O
336 molecules. Therefore, the interaction between CO₂ molecules and H₂O molecules will
337 not significantly affect the stability of the ice structure. A water molecule in liquid
338 water can always form four hydrogen bonds with adjacent water molecules. Obviously,

339 the strength of four hydrogen bonds in liquid water is not equal, and the strength of
340 one hydrogen bond is significantly weaker than the other three hydrogen bonds. The
341 simulation results in this paper can guide the practical applications, for example, in
342 order to quickly complete the process of converting gas CO₂ to CO₂ hydrate,
343 pre-adding CO₂ hydrate seeds to the target solution is the most economical and
344 labor-saving method.

345 However, this is a double-edged sword situation. People can indeed store a large
346 amount of CO₂ in the ocean in the form of hydrate, up to now, people are still unable
347 to cope with natural disasters such as earthquakes, tsunamis, typhoons and volcanic
348 eruptions. Once a large amount of stored CO₂ is released when natural disasters strike,
349 it is like opening the Pandora's box. How should we deal with the massive storage of
350 CO₂ and how to turn wastes into treasures? This is a problem worthy of common
351 consideration by all people in the world.

352 **Authorship Contribution**

353 Xianwu Jing: Idea, Investigation, Model establishment, Conceptualization,
354 Visualization, Writing- original draft, Writing-review & editing. Lili Chen: Idea,
355 Project administration, Supervision. Youquan Liu: Idea, Project administration,
356 Supervision. Ziyi Fu: Idea, Investigation, Writing-review & editing.

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360 **Data Availability Statement**

361 All input files are listed in the support information, so anyone can repeat our
362 work as long as they follow the commands without any efforts. All the data that
363 support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding
364 authors.

365 **Conflicts of Interest**

366 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

367 **Sample Availability**

368 Samples of the compounds are not available from the authors.

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